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Test cases and applications

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Highlights

- Transport of last mile distribution with multiple performance criteria considered
- A new model with different assumptions and closer to operation is presented
- Three validated test cases are provided for the problem, one of them unpublished
- Test cases data are provided and a website maintaining test cases will be available
- Data provided allows and encourages replicability and model comparison

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

Multi-criteria optimization for last mile distribution of disaster relief aid: Test cases and applications

José M. Ferrer¹, F. Javier Martín-Campo², M. Teresa Ortuño², Alfonso J. Pedraza-Martínez³, Gregorio Tirado¹, Begoña Vitoriano²

Abstract

Humanitarian organizations transport large quantities of aid for distribution in the aftermath of disasters. Transportation for last mile distribution includes multiple, and often conflicting, performance criteria that include time (deprivation), cost, coverage, equity and security. We build a compromise programming model for multi-criteria optimization in humanitarian last mile distribution. Regarding security, ours is the first multi-criteria model able to produce an actual vehicle schedule while forcing vehicles to form convoys in humanitarian operations research. We illustrate the multi-criteria optimization using a realistic test case based on the Pakistan floods, 2010. We standardize and share this case as well as cases based on the Niger famine, 2005 and the Haiti earthquake, 2010. By sharing test cases, we encourage basic scientific tasks such as replicability and model comparison within the humanitarian operations research community.

Keywords: Humanitarian Logistics, Multi-criteria Optimization, Test Cases, Last Mile Distribution

1. Introduction

Humanitarian organizations transport large quantities of aid for distribution in the aftermath of disasters. Transportation for last mile distribution includes multiple, and often conflicting, performance criteria that include time (deprivation), cost, coverage, and equity. Additionally, security is an increasingly important criterion to optimize in operations that are carried out in environments of armed conflict and social unrest (Pedraza-Martinez and Van Wassenhove 2016). The United Nations report that attacks to their official vehicles

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more than tripled from 2014 with 45 attacks to 2015 with 155 attacks (United Nations 2016, p.4). Transportation security could be improved by either using convoys or choosing safer routes, but these strategies would oppose other criteria such as cost, time and equity. Organizations need to consider multiple criteria simultaneously. This is why the use of multi-criteria optimization in humanitarian operations research is growing rapidly (Gutjahr and Nolz 2016).

We build a compromise programming model for multi-criteria optimization in humanitarian last mile distribution. Under some regularity conditions, compromise programming ensures that the obtained solution is efficient or non-dominated (i.e. no other solution can improve all the criteria simultaneously). Our model provides a solution as close as possible to the ideal point formed by the optimal values of the criteria considered individually. Moreover, the model includes security issues that force vehicles to travel in convoys (making easier escort tasks) as well as criteria related to efficiency (cost), effectiveness (time, coverage, reliability) and equity (Gutjahr and Nolz 2016). Extant literature considering convoys (Ortuño et al. 2011, Vitoriano et al. 2011) does so using network flow models and does not provide the individual vehicle routing directly. Ours is the first multi-criteria model able to produce an actual vehicle schedule while forcing vehicles to form convoys in humanitarian operations research (OR). We capture the current conditions of conflict and social unrest that many humanitarian organizations face in reality.

The model application uses a realistic test case based on the Pakistan floods, 2010 to illustrate the multi-criteria optimization. We standardize and share this case as well as cases based on the Niger famine, 2005 and the Haiti earthquake, 2010. The three cases have salient characteristics that make them valuable for benchmarking. Our website (www.mat.ucm.es/humlog) includes comprehensive case descriptions, original raw data and data updates made in 2017. The data are not only ready to use in software packages such as GAMS but also available in Excel tables. The cases form the basis of the first battery of humanitarian OR cases to be publicly available.

Humanitarian OR needs realistic test cases to replicate experiments, validate models and compare results. However, getting realistic data on humanitarian operations is challenging (Starr and Van Wassenhove 2014, Pedraza-Martinez and Van Wassenhove 2016). Confidentiality agreements and/or high acquisition costs discourage data sharing within the humanitarian OR community. It is our belief that having a public battery of realistic test cases will benefit the area of humanitarian OR and will, in turn, have a positive impact for practitioners and beneficiaries.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the problem of transportation for last mile distribution, followed by a literature review related to the research problem and the use of test cases in operations research

in Section 3. The compromise programming model is presented in Section 4 and solved in Section 5 using the Pakistan floods 2010. Section 6 introduces two other test cases to be available in the repository, Niger famine
40 2005 and Haiti earthquake 2010. Section 7 presents our conclusions. The appendix shows the complete model.

2. Transportation for last mile distribution

Following the characterization included in the Logistics Operational Guide (LOG) of the Logistics Cluster
45 ⁴, “the distribution chain or channel represents the movement of a product or service from the point of purchase to the time it is handed over to the final user/consumer. Some of the distribution activities embrace materials handling, storage and warehousing, packaging, transportation, etc.” Planning for the last mile of the distribu-
tion chain includes defining missions for each of the different organizations involved in the disaster-response operation. Organizations often focus their operations on sectors such as nutrition or water, hygiene and sanitation. Based on these activities, organizations define the type of humanitarian aid that they will handle as well as a particular geographic area or subset of beneficiaries that they will assist. Moreover, since response
50 activities extend over several weeks or months, distribution operations usually repeat over time. These begin at hubs and regional warehouses and end at field warehouses or at extended delivery points (EDP), where EDP refers to the point at which organizations physically hand over supplies to a counterpart such as an implementing partner, an individual, or the beneficiaries themselves (Logistic Cluster (2017), version 13, page 140). Depending on the nature of the disaster, transportation management for disaster relief can be complex.
55 It is contingent on budget, demand coverage, road reliability, equity, security in the disaster area and other criteria.

Information availability and the scope of the mission strongly affect transportation planning for last mile distribution. Organizations obtain information through the assessment of the situation in the aftermath of the disaster. The assessment is one of the first logistics tasks to be performed (together with activities such as rescue
60 and evacuation), especially after sudden onset disasters. Phase 1 of the assessment develops a preliminary scenario definition in the first 72 hours following the disaster, as shown in the Multi-Cluster/Sector Initial Rapid Assessment (MIRA) report of the United Nations Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC 2012). Phase 2 obtains the MIRA Report within two weeks of the disaster in order to inform in-depth response planning and revised appeals, where applicable. During this phase, organizations define responsibilities, allocate tasks,

⁴<http://dlca.logcluster.org/display/LOG>, [Last access: June 14th 2017]

65 collect primary data and analyze secondary data. Usually, after two weeks organizations have (relatively accurate) information related to consequences assessment although the greater the consequences are, the longer it takes to get accurate information. Based on information that improves over time, organizations plan distribution activities.

This research investigates transportation for last mile distribution. It focuses on secondary movements that 70 may involve multiple deliveries within a defined area, such as from a regional or local warehouse to EDPs. We also include primary movements in bulk between two specific locations within a limited area, as, for example, between two warehouses or from a port or railhead to a warehouse. Regarding information, the problem we model refers to phase 2, in which some information is available instead of the immediate aftermath of the disaster that is characterized by high uncertainty (demand, state of infrastructure, resources required, time 75 needed to develop the operation), dispersion of resources and high time pressure (short runtime model and short time to prepare the model).

3. Literature review

We discuss two aspects of the humanitarian OR literature. First, we classify previous works based on multi-criteria models for humanitarian last mile transportation. Second, we discuss the use of test cases in 80 OR and its extension for humanitarian OR.

3.1. Multi-criteria optimization for humanitarian logistics

Last mile distribution planning during a disaster relief operation is an inherently multi-criteria problem. Gralla et al. (2014) interview a panel of humanitarian experts and find that the most important logistics criteria during disaster relief are: total cargo distributed, location and item priority, speed of delivery and 85 cost. Gutjahr and Nolz (2016) present an extensive review on multi-criteria optimization in humanitarian OR. The authors classify criteria in three categories: efficiency (i.e. cost), effectiveness (i.e. time, coverage, travel distance, reliability and security) and equity (fairness). We model the three categories by including cost, time, coverage, reliability, security and equity. We do not model travel distance because it is proportional to cost and time. Gutjahr and Nolz (2016) classify the literature as deterministic or stochastic and pre-disaster or 90 post-disaster. We build a post-disaster deterministic model in the sense that uncertainty is included through estimated parameters instead of considering random variable distributions or scenarios. Hoyos et al. (2015) present a survey for stochastic models in disaster management. Regarding relief supply chain activities, Habib et al. (2016) classify models into categories that include facility location, relief distribution and evacuation.

Our literature review concentrates on deterministic models of relief distribution, in which the transportation
 95 model is the core of the research (Table 1).

Columns 2-7 of Table 1 show the optimization criteria used in transportation models. Extant literature
 overlooks the security criterion as it appears only twice in the literature. Ortuño et al. (2011) propose a
 security objective based on the maximum probability of suffering an assault across an arc, which is extended
 in Vitoriano et al. (2011). Additionally, they consider convoys as a strict security condition but do not include
 100 vehicle routing. Even though researchers have overlooked security, Pedraza-Martinez and Van Wassenhove
 (2016) remark that more armed conflicts may increase security issues in the future. Thus, humanitarian OR
 needs more research involving the security criterion and its trade-offs with well studied criteria such cost,
 equity, coverage and reliability and time.

Time is the most common criterion in transportation models. Papers propose the total waiting time for
 105 each demand (Chen et al. 2011), the sum of travel times (Nolz et al. 2011, Huang et al. 2012), the sum of the
 delivery times (Huang et al. 2012), the total delay cost (Huang et al. 2015) or the maximal travel time (Nolz
 et al. 2011). The cost criterion may include the cost for vehicles to return to their origin depots. The equity
 criterion models fairness in distribution (Ortuño et al. 2011, Tirado et al. 2014) or as fairness in the delivery
 times (Nolz et al. 2011, Huang et al. 2012). The coverage criterion refers to the total met demand, but in
 110 some cases, it only includes either certain priority nodes (Ortuño et al. 2011) or priority weights of nodes or
 commodities (Lin et al. 2011). Finally, reliability is a criterion related to the probability that the network arcs
 will be available for transportation. This reliability measure comprises the least reliable arc used (Ortuño et
 al. 2011, Vitoriano et al. 2011), all the arcs included in the solution (Nolz et al. 2011, Vitoriano et al. 2011)
 or the number of alternative paths between two demand nodes (Nolz et al. 2011).

Column 8 of Table 1 shows solution approaches to address multi-criteria models. Approaches have been
 115 classified in scalarization (SC), Pareto optimization (PO), goal programming (GP) and compromise program-
 ming (CP). Scalarization refers to models whose objective function is the aggregation of the single objectives,
 usually through weighted sums. Usually, scalarization is not classified as a multi-criteria method unless the
 weights vary systematically or through interactive methods. Pareto optimization methods try to reduce the
 120 solutions set by obtaining the Pareto frontier, defined as the set of all efficient solutions in the objectives space.
 A solution is efficient if no other solution provides better or equal values for all the criteria. Although Pareto
 optimization does not require predefined objective preferences, it is useful only for few criteria.

Compromise programming and goal programming are particular cases of the reference point method, whose
 aim is to obtain a solution as close as possible to a given reference point (see [46] and a complete revision of this

125 method in [47]). If the reference point is the ideal of the problem (formed by the best possible solution for each
criterion individually optimized), then it is a compromise programming method (Zeleny 1973). If the reference
point is a satisficing (satisfying and suffice) point formed by target values for the different criteria, then it is
a goal programming method (Charnes and Cooper (1961), [36]). The two methods differ in nature and the
characteristics of the solutions they provide. Goal programming does not ensure reaching an efficient solution,
130 but it gives a solution that satisfies the goals of decision makers, or if this is not possible, the closest solution to
such goals. On the contrary, under some regularity conditions, compromise programming ensures that no other
solution has better or equal values for all the criteria. Both methods relate through the mathematical concept
of distance to a given reference point. The concept of distance can use different metrics but the most common
ones are L_1 (absolute deviations, also known as the aggregation for majorities), L_2 (Euclidean distance) and
135 L_∞ (Tchebycheff distance, which minimizes the maximum distance). The distance measure includes weights
for the criteria reflecting the importance given to each of them. When the importance of different criteria
cannot be compared, it is possible to define their priority levels and lexicographical optimization can prevent
the trade-off between them.

Columns 9-20 of Table 1 show different models' attributes. The attribute "Convoys" refers to models that
140 force vehicles to travel together through the arcs due security issues. Previous models that include convoys
(Ortuño et al. 2011, Vitoriano et al. 2011) do not provide the individual vehicle scheduling. "Shortage"
indicates that there is not enough available aid to meet the demand fully, so making aid allocation decisions
is necessary. Besides, models can be multimodal (including different types of vehicles), multidepot (including
multiple supply nodes and/or multiple vehicle initial locations), multiloading (each vehicle can load multiple
145 times, even in the same node). Models can split delivery or carry out transshipments in any node. Also, vehicles
can visit the same node more than once or not (repeating nodes). "Multiperiod" refers to periods with different
data values (e.g. amount of load available or demanded). When models use static data we classify them as
single-period models. We introduce a deterministic transportation model that includes objectives such as time,
cost, equity, priority, security and reliability for last mile distribution of humanitarian aid. The routing model
150 incorporates security issues forcing travel in convoys, which have not been analyzed in the literature until now.

Reference	Opt. criteria and approach										Model characteristics									
	Security	Time	Cost	Equity	Coverage	Reliability	Multic. Approach*	Convoys	Individual scheduling	Shortage	Multimodal	Multidepot	Multiloading	Split delivery	Transshipment	Return of vehicles	Repeating nodes	Multiperiod	Multicommodity	
Balcik et al. (2008)			✓	✓			SC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Berkoune et al. (2012)		✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Campbell et al. (2008)		✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Chen et al. (2011)		✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Haghani and Oh (1996)			✓					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Huang et al. (2012)		✓		✓			SC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Huang et al. (2015)		✓		✓	✓		SC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Ke and Feng (2013)		✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Lin et al. (2011)		✓		✓			SC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Nolz et al. (2011)		✓					PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Ortuño et al. (2011)		✓		✓			GP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Özdamar et al. (2004)		✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Sharif and Salari (2015)			✓					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Tirado et al. (2014)		✓	✓				GP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Viswanath and Peeta (2003)		✓					PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Vitoriano et al. (2011)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	GP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Present Work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

* (SC) Scalarization, (PO) Pareto Optimization, (GP) Goal Programming, (CP) Compromise Programming.

Table 1: Optimization criteria, multi-criteria approach and model characteristics

3.2. Test cases in humanitarian OR

OR uses test cases to calibrate models. However, test cases in OR are different from case studies conducted in qualitative research. In contrast to qualitative case studies that are used for theory building (Eisenhardt 1989, McCutcheon and Meredith 1993, Ellram 1996, Voss et al. 2002), test cases in OR are data repositories to replicate, validate and compare models and methods. For example, test cases can help investigate the widely studied traveling salesman problem (Applegate et al. 2006, Hoffman et al. 2013). In order to encourage replication and comparison of the countless solution methods proposed in the literature, the OR community created a traveling salesman problem library of instance data sets called TSPLIB (Reinelt 1991). The TSPLIB provides a broad set of test instances, and each of them includes a short description, together with the best-known lower and upper bounds.

Multi-criteria optimization research uses test cases as well. In the area of dynamic multi-objective optimization, Farina et al. (2004) share five test cases to inspire researchers to propose more efficient solution algorithms in the future. Zhou et al. (2011) remark that in dynamic multi-objective optimization the work of Farina et al. (2004) was the first step towards the standardization of modeling approaches. Within the OR tradition, test cases provide raw data for replication, validation and comparison.

Humanitarian OR researchers need realistic data and test cases to replicate experiments, validate models and compare results. Due to these issues, most published papers on multi-criteria optimization of humanitarian aid use either generated data sets (e.g. Abounacer et al. 2014) or realistic but private data sets that hinder replication and comparison (Vitoriano et al. 2011, Ortuño et al. 2011, Wang et al. 2014). To improve data sharing within the humanitarian OR community, we build and make available three test cases that are composed of realistic data from disasters that actually occurred. These test cases are necessary to advance research in the area of last mile distribution in humanitarian operations.

4. A compromise programming model for last mile transportation of humanitarian aid

We contribute to the debate on objective functions and multi-criteria optimization in humanitarian OR by introducing a compromise programming model for last mile distribution of humanitarian aid. The routing model provides a detailed schedule for each vehicle, which is a novelty among models that take convoys into account for security reasons. The problem focuses on an organization performing last mile distribution. It assumes that information about assets (e.g. available aid in warehouses, available vehicle fleet) and demand is known with enough accuracy to design the operation.

180 The general mission concerns a single commodity (usually a kit prepared in a warehouse or a product provided by one supplier), but could be easily adapted to make it multicommodity, if required. The problem consists of finding the optimal routes for transporting a fixed amount of aid from supply nodes (such as ports, airports and warehouses) to demand nodes (EDPs such as temporary camps or distribution points). The model finds the best routes to transport aid and calculates the required vehicle fleet size. The available fleet
185 may be part of the organization's fleet or may be available for rental. The model is multimodal (different types of vehicles), multidepot (several supply locations), multiloading (multiple loading and unloading of a vehicle), allows split delivery and carries out transshipments. Since the vehicles are treated individually, the characteristics of each vehicle j are those of the corresponding type $veh(j)$. Table 2 shows model indices, data and variables.

190 The model makes nine assumptions. First, due to security reasons, all vehicles traversing an arc must travel together forming a convoy (an arc is traversed at most once), which allows escorts. This assumption implicitly induces a precedence relation on the arcs and limits the number of movements through arcs that a vehicle can do (called vehicle stages). Besides, this assumption bounds the number of times a convoy arrives or leaves a node, which are called node events. The number of node events is bound by the node degree (number of arcs
195 directly connected to the node). Each node event has an associated time in the solution and it equals zero for events that do not take place. The assumption of one arc being traversed at most once can be relaxed through arc duplication.

Second, the ransack probability decreases with the size of the convoy (until a minimum level reached for a certain size, being constant for larger convoys). Third, transshipment can use any node. Fourth, the itinerary
200 of a vehicle ends when the vehicle makes its last delivery. In order to approximate the total cost, each vehicle must return to its node of origin following the least expensive path. Fifth, there are different types of vehicles, which are characterized by their capacity, maximum speed and cost. A certain number of vehicles of each type is available at each network node. Sixth, there may be access restrictions for some types of vehicles through some arcs. An arc can be unsuitable for some kinds of vehicles if the arc is too narrow or sloping or if the
205 road surface makes it too difficult to be traversed. Larger vehicles have more restrictions. Seventh, due to the uncertainty about the damages to the transport network (either by lack of information in the aftermath or by unexpected effects), each arc has a probability of being available. Arc unavailability can lead to delays and undelivered load. Using unreliable arcs is penalized through the future deliveries of vehicles traveling in the convoy. Thus, the most unreliable arcs should be avoided. Eighth, node priority levels can be set for demand
210 nodes in order to force aid distribution to locations especially difficult to reach. Otherwise, these nodes could

be ignored when optimizing other criteria, like time or cost.

Finally, an amount of aid for distribution defines a mission, which is carried out with limited budget. Often, the amount to be distributed by vehicles in a single itinerary is less than the demand for a longer period and less than the available supplies. However, if the mission is intended to distribute as much as possible in one go, this amount can be set to the minimum of the total demand and the total supply. Since the mission is intended to distribute in one go, the model does not contemplate vehicle trip repetition. Therefore, the model could not be suitable for missions that mix long trips and very short trips. To prevent this issue, a geographic region could be divided in areas before using the model.

The model takes six criteria into account: time, cost, equity, priority, security and reliability. These criteria capture the key aspects of efficiency, effectiveness and equity identified by Gutjahr and Nolz (2016). We opt for the following measures regarding the performance criteria, which were previously used in Ferrer et al. (2016) but not in the context of a mathematical programming model.

Time refers to the instant when the last delivery is made (after the last vehicle stage occurs); $TIME \geq T_{i,deg_i} \quad \forall i$.

Cost includes the transportation cost, approximate handling cost and return cost (through the cheapest route from the last node visited). The Dijkstra's algorithm can compute these return values easily and quickly. Cost is bound by the budget,

$$\begin{aligned}
 COST &= \sum_{k,j} \text{dist}_k \left(cv_{k,j} L_{k,j} + cf_{k,j} \sum_s X_{k,j,s} \right) + cu \sum_{j,s} \left(Q1_{j,s} + Q2_{j,s} \right) + \\
 &+ \sum_{i,j} \text{cback}_{j,i} \left(\sum_{s,k|\text{end}_k=i} X_{k,j,s} - \sum_{s,k|\text{beg}_k=i} X_{k,j,s} \right) \\
 COST &\leq b.
 \end{aligned}$$

Equity adds the squared deviations of satisfied demand from the most equitable proportion that can be reached delivering $qglobal$: $\text{idp} = \frac{qglobal}{\sum_i \text{dem}_i}$. The square root could be ignored in order to obtain a quadratic model, but it should be taken into account when joining it with other criteria. Besides, a minimum level of demand fulfillment at each node could also be included as a hard constraint. However, minimum demand fulfillment would restrict the feasible space, which could lead either to solutions that could affect other criteria or an infeasible problem,

Notation	Description
<u>Network structure:</u>	
(N, A)	Relief network. N is the set of nodes. A is the set of arcs (one-way)
$i, i' \in N$	Node indices
$k, k', k'' \in A$	Arc indices. $k = (i, i')$, $i, i' \in N$
$dist_k$	Length of arc k
$velc_k$	Maximum speed through arc k
r_k	Availability probability at arc k
p_k	Ransack probability at arc k with a single vehicle traveling
q_k	Minimum ransack probability on arc k
c_k	Size of a convoy for which the minimum ransack probability is reached on arc k
<u>Supply, demand and priority:</u>	
dem_i	Demand at node i expressed in units of load
qav_i	Supply at node i expressed in units of load. $dem_i = qav_i = 0$ for transshipment nodes
pr_i	Priority level of node i
<u>Fleet:</u>	
VT	Set of vehicle types
$v \in VT$	Vehicle type index
cap_v	Capacity of vehicle type v in units of load
$velv_v$	Maximum speed of vehicle type v
$vav_{v,i}$	Availability of vehicle type v at node i
$cf_{k,v}$	Fixed cost of vehicle type v through arc k per unit of length (empty travel cost)
$cv_{k,v}$	Variable cost of vehicle type v through arc k per unit of length and load (load travel cost)
cu, tu	Unit cost and time of handling load (loading or unloading) of a vehicle
$comp_{k,v}$	Compatibility between arc k and vehicle type v . $comp_{k,v} = 1$ if vehicle type v can use arc k , $comp_{k,v} = 0$ otherwise
<u>Mission global parameters:</u>	
$qglobal$	Total amount of aid (load) to be distributed in the operation
b	Available budget for the operation
<u>Indices:</u>	
$j \in V$	Single vehicle index
$veh(j) \in VT$	Type of vehicle j
$s, s' \in \{1, 2, \dots, A \}$	Vehicle stage indices
$e(i), e'(i) \in \{0, 1, \dots, deg_i\}$	Node event indices for node i
<u>Auxiliary parameters:</u>	
deg_i	Degree of node i
beg_k, end_k	Beginning node of arc k and end node of arc k , respectively.
ori_j	Origin node of vehicle j
$cback_{j,i}$	Return cost of vehicle j from node i to its origin node using the least expensive path
<u>Decision variables:</u>	
D_k	Traveling time, time required for the convoy to travel through arc k
$L_{k,j}$	Amount of load carried through arc k by vehicle j
$P_{k,k'}$	Binary variable taking value 1 if arc k precedes arc k'
$X_{k,j,s}$	Binary variable taking value 1 if vehicle j traverses arc k at its stage s
$S_{i,e(i)}$	Stock, amount of load available at node i after node event $e(i)$
$T_{i,e(i)}$	Node event time, time when node event $e(i)$ occurs
$Z_{i,k,e(i)}$	Binary variable taking value 1 if node event $e(i)$ corresponds to arc k
AL_k	Aid delivery planned affected by the unavailability of arc k
PR_k	Ransack probability for a convoy traversing arc k
$LS_{k,j,s}$	Amount of aid loaded through arc k by vehicle j in its stage s
$Q1_{j,s}, Q2_{j,s}$	Defect and excess, respectively, of load carried by vehicle j in its stage $s + 1$ with respect to s
<u>Objective variables:</u>	
$TIME =$ Time; $COST =$ Cost; $EQU =$ Equity; $PRI =$ Priority; $SECU =$ Security; $RELI =$ Reliability.	

Table 2: Notation: Indices, data and variables

$$EQUI = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\{i | dem_i > 0\}|} \sum_{i | dem_i > 0} \left(\frac{S_{i,deg(i)}}{dem_i} - idp \right)^2}.$$

Priority weights the sum of relative unsatisfied demands over all demand nodes by their priority levels. It increases the relevance of nodes of difficult access,

$$PRIO = \sum_{i | pri_i > 0} pri_i \left(1 - \frac{S_{i,deg(i)}}{dem_i} \right).$$

Reliability is the sum of the probabilities of arcs being unavailable multiplied by the affected deliveries, which are those scheduled in later stages for the vehicles in the convoy traversing the arc. This metric can be interpreted as expected affected delivery. $LS_{k,j,s}$ represents the amount of aid loaded through arc k by vehicle j in its stage s , and $Q1_{j,s}$ and $Q2_{j,s}$ represent the defect and excess of load being carried by vehicle j in its stage $s + 1$ with respect to its previous stage, respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} Q1_{j,s} - Q2_{j,s} &= \sum_k LS_{k,j,s} - \sum_k LS_{k,j,s+1} \\ AL_{k,j,s} &\geq \sum_{s' / s' > s} Q1_{j,s'} - qglobal(1 - X_{k,j,s}) \\ RELI &= \sum_k (1 - r_k) \sum_{j,s} AL_{k,j,s}. \end{aligned}$$

Security refers to expected losses due to assaults, defined as the sum of the load being carried through an arc multiplied by the probability of the convoy suffering an assault. We consider that the probability of suffering an assault decreases with the convoy size, defining a quadratic polynomial function of the number of vehicles traveling together. This quadratic decreasing ends at convoy size c_k , considering that ransack probability for bigger convoys is constant.

$$SECU = \sum_k PR_k \sum_j L_{k,j}$$

$$PR_k = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} = 0 \\ p_k + \frac{p_k - q_k}{(c_k - 1)^2} \left(\left(\sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \right)^2 - 2c_k \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} + 2c_k - 1 \right) & \text{if } 1 \leq \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \leq c_k \\ q_k & \text{if } \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} > c_k \end{cases}$$

The aim of the multiple criteria model is to minimize the performance criteria considered:

$$\min(TIME, COST, EQUI, PRIO, RELI, SECU)$$

Following the compromise programming methodology, the best solution is the efficient solution closest to the ideal point. The objective function of compromise programming is as follows:

$$L_p = \left[\sum_g w_g \left(\frac{f_g - \text{ideal}_g}{\text{anti}_g - \text{ideal}_g} \right)^p \right]^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad p \geq 1.$$

Weight w_g represents the importance that the decision maker gives to objective g ; f_g is the measure of objective g ; ideal_g and anti_g are the coordinates of the ideal point and the nadir (or anti-ideal) point corresponding to objective g , respectively. The worst values for the objectives in the efficient set of solutions form the nadir point. The model normalizes the objectives, taking $\frac{f_g - \text{ideal}_g}{\text{anti}_g - \text{ideal}_g}$ values between 0 and 1 into the efficient set. The value of p ($1 \leq p \leq \infty$) determines the metric defined. This model achieves an efficient solution if conditions, such as strictly positive weights, linearity and $p < \infty$, are satisfied.

The rest of the constraints can be seen in the Appendix, which displays the complete model. With simple changes as commented before, the model would be a mixed integer quadratic model, but convexity is not guaranteed. This extensive model illustrates the complexity of working with convoys to mitigate security issues while obtaining a precise schedule for each vehicle and modeling multiple performance criteria. Model dimensions for real cases could be big enough to require heuristic methods to obtain solutions fast enough to be useful.

5. Model application: results of the Pakistan floods test case

We illustrate the compromise programming model application using a test case based on the Pakistan floods 2010, described in this section. The test case includes a brief description and all the data needed to solve our model.

5.1. Pakistan floods (2010)

During the summer of 2010 (July 28th to August 8th), severe floods hit Pakistan due to heavy monsoon rains that affected the regions of Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab and Sindh as well as the Indus River Valley. At the beginning of August, water covered one fifth of the country. According to Pakistani government sources, the floods affected 20 million people and increased the risk of gastroenteritis, diarrhea and skin diseases. Moreover, the floods severely affected the electrical infrastructure of the country. Flooding damaged 4,000 km of roads and more than 5,000 km of railroads. The mission set out for this case takes place in the southwest Punjab region, which was the most populated in the country and one of the most affected by floods. A brief summary of the Pakistan case is included in Table 3. An extensive case description as well as the raw data are available in our website www.mat.ucm.es/humlog.

5.2. Pakistan test case results

The number of multiple criteria added up to the large network (41 nodes, 106 directed arcs) lead to a high dimension problem. These reasons justify the use of a heuristic solution approach. We selected the heuristic method Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedure (GRASP) for several reasons. First, in our model, the linkages between the different elements that comprise a feasible solution make it very difficult to perform changes without losing feasibility. Second, even checking the feasibility and the variation of the objective function of any small potential modification, together with the operations required to implement it and reconstruct the solution, would require a very high computational effort. Hence, we discard evolutionary algorithms and local search-based metaheuristics to concentrate on the GRASP method, which has a strong constructive component.

GRASP is based on an elite set (set of solutions) containing solutions with good values in the objectives. The elite set is initialized with a constructive algorithm and improves after each iteration. The intuition behind this heuristic is that if an element appears frequently in a set of good diverse solutions, it must be good and, thus, should have a higher probability to be selected when building new feasible solutions. Local search is applied to the new feasible solution, if it improves, the elite set updates and replaces one of the former elite

Pakistan	
Place	Pakistan (Asia)
Year	2010
Type of disaster	Floods
N. affected people	20 million
<p>Brief description: Pakistan suffers from severe flooding due to monsoon rains.</p>	
<p>Mission: The mission takes place in the southwest Punjab region, which was the most populated in the country and one of the most affected by floods. Three towns have 1,500 tons of humanitarian aid available for distribution: Taunsa (300 tons), Multan (750 tons) and Janpur (450 tons). The objective is to distribute 1,000 tons of this humanitarian aid to an extensive area where the affected population is located in dispersed villages. A budget of \$1.5 million (USD) is available for the operation.</p>	
<p>Availability and demand: Availability and demand can be accessed on www.mat.ucm.es/humlog.</p>	
<p>Network and data: The network is composed of 41 nodes and 53 symmetric arcs (106 directed arcs). Note that the reduced number of arcs is due to the large number of damaged roads near the Indus Valley. Three of the 41 nodes are supply nodes (Taunsa, Multan and Janpur, numbered as 1, 2 and 3, respectively); there are 26 demand nodes and 12 transshipment nodes.</p> <p>Three types of trucks are available. Type 1 trucks have three ton capacity and a maximum speed of 100 km/h; type 2 trucks have a twenty-five ton capacity and a maximum speed of 60 km/h; type 3 trucks have a fifteen ton capacity and a maximum speed of 80 km/h. The availability of these vehicles in the different towns is assumed to be known.</p>	
<p>Distances, Ransack probabilities, Reliabilities matrices and Available fleet (per city): The raw data for symmetric arcs are available in our website.</p>	
<p>Data sources: The Logistic Cluster website provides most of the data. The map corresponds to the one published on September 20th (elaborated on September 17th), entitled Map-Road Conditions-SW Punjab Province as of 17 September 2010 and available online⁵. The Logistic Cluster website⁶, the IFRC website⁷ and media sources such as The Guardian's website⁸ provide situation reports and concept operations.</p> <p>(2) http://www.logcluster.org/sites/default/files/maps/Logcluster_PAK_014C_A2P_20100917.pdf, [Last access: 06th November, 2017], (3) http://www.logcluster.org, [Last access: 06th November, 2017], (4) http://www.ifrc.org/en/publications-and-reports/appeals/, [Last access: 06th November, 2017], (5) https://www.theguardian.com/world/2010/aug/09/weather-hampers-pakistan-flood-relief, [Last access: 06th November, 2017]</p>	
<p>Tested in: The test case was built as the final degree project of [2] and studied extensively in the Ph.D. thesis of [13]. A mathematical model testing the case has not been published to date.</p>	
<p>Further information: www.mat.ucm.es/humlog</p>	

Table 3: Pakistan Test Case Description.

Algorithm 1 GRASP algorithm

```

1: for  $i = 1, \dots, m$  do
2:   Build a new solution  $S$  with the Randomized Constructive Algorithm.
3: end for
4: Select the best solution  $S^*$ .
5: Create the initial elite set.
6: for  $i = 1, \dots, n$  do
7:   Build a new solution  $S$  with the Elite Set Constructive Algorithm.
8:   Update the elite set and the best solution  $S^*$ .
9:   Increase the weight of the elite set used to generate new solutions
10: end for
11: Output  $S^*$ .

```

solutions. Algorithm 1 presents the summarized pseudocode. The algorithm was published in Ferrer et al. (2016) and was used in Ferrer (2016) as well, where results were validated through comparing them with the published results related to the other test cases. Specification details can be seen in Ferrer et al. (2016). We implemented GRASP metaheuristic in Fortran 95 and executed it on a computer cluster with an Intel Xeon E5645 processor with 2.4 Ghz and 4Gb RAM running Linux 5.7. When running, the algorithm performed 25,000 iterations per execution, where each iteration provided a feasible solution. It took 370 seconds to solve the model.

Optimizing each objective separately (using mono-objective models) produces the payoff matrix (Table 4). Each row shows all objective values when optimizing the respective objective. Note that for the priority criterion, pri_i has been set to 1 for Rojhan, node 26 and to 0 for all other nodes. In order to construct the objective function of compromise programming, the main diagonal of the payoff matrix is the ideal point (Table 4). Obtaining the nadir point is more complicated since efficient solutions with better values than those observed in the payoff matrix can exist. This issue affects the normalization of the objectives which can distort the meaning of the weights. Nevertheless, the computational effort required to obtain the nadir point does not seem justified for normalization purposes, and we approximate the nadir values with the worst observed values in the payoff matrix. The objective values of the compromise solution are given on the last row of Table 4. This solution is still optimal for the priority, but in order to obtain a balanced solution, it has been necessary to worsen other objectives, which illustrates the conflict between different criteria.

We use the L_2 metric in order to penalize the longest distances to the optimum of individual objectives more and with equal weights for all objectives. In practice the value of these weights should be agreed upon by decision makers. This could involve interactions with them until they establish the importance of

	T	C	E	P	S	R
Time	1.95	911.89	0.44	1.00	380.55	365.25
Cost	2.48	731.24	0.45	1.00	364.78	370.00
Equity	6.38	1387.37	0.19	0.39	537.27	583.00
Priority	7.24	1436.20	0.40	0.00	455.02	915.75
Security	5.18	1352.48	0.48	0.00	3.62	659.75
Reliability	3.02	953.88	0.46	1.00	408.05	238.25
Ideal point	1.95	731.24	0.19	0.00	3.62	238.25
Estimated nadir point	7.24	1436.20	0.48	1.00	537.27	915.75
Compromise solution (using L_2)	4.04	1031.85	0.33	0.00	232.26	481.25

Table 4: Pakistan test case results: Payoff Matrix, Ideal and Estimated Nadir Point, Compromise Solution. Columns represent objectives values, while rows represent solutions.

310 each objective. Decision makers can utilize this interactive approach through an interface allowing weight modifications. Before using the application, i.e. before the disaster occurs, the model calibration needs to be performed. Calibration refers to defining the relative importance of different criteria as well as the accepted levels reliability and security. During this calibration, users not only can provide their preferences but also can validate the results on test cases, in order to utilize the results of the model as support for decision making
315 later.

Node	qav (t)	rem (t)
<i>n1</i>	300	85
<i>n2</i>	750	355
<i>n3</i>	450	60

qav: Supply rem: Remaining aid

Table 5: Compromise solution - supply nodes

Table 5 shows the amount of aid available originally and at the end in the supply nodes, and Table 6 illustrates the amount delivered to each demand node and the time to reach it. Note that node n_{26} is considered a high priority node because of its difficult access, but 100% of its demand is satisfied. It takes approximately four hours at a cost of \$1.03 million (USD) to perform aid distribution. The operation time
320 does not include loading and unloading times.

Node	dem (t)	sat (%)	end time (h)	Node	dem (t)	sat (%)	end time (h)
<i>n4</i>	40	100	1.38	<i>n5</i>	20	100	1.64
<i>n6</i>	110	0	–	<i>n7</i>	75	33.3	1.84
<i>n8</i>	25	100	0.84	<i>n9</i>	75	66.7	1.80
<i>n10</i>	70	61.4	1.06	<i>n11</i>	30	83.3	1.41
<i>n12</i>	90	100	1.38	<i>n13</i>	40	67.5	1.62
<i>n14</i>	75	100	0.82	<i>n15</i>	60	66.7	1.73
<i>n16</i>	65	73.8	2.13	<i>n17</i>	35	71.4	1.78
<i>n18</i>	65	61.5	1.41	<i>n19</i>	30	50	1.46
<i>n20</i>	75	80	1.44	<i>n21</i>	25	68	2.83
<i>n22</i>	85	100	0.86	<i>n23</i>	120	0	–
<i>n24</i>	25	100	0.81	<i>n25</i>	20	100	0.85
<i>n26</i>	85	100	4.04	<i>n27</i>	50	100	1.02
<i>n28</i>	50	0	–	<i>n29</i>	70	100	2.01

dem: Demand sat: Percentage of satisfied demand end time: End time

Table 6: Compromise solution - demand nodes

The solution moves 65 vehicles: 16 of Type 1, 19 of Type 2 and 30 of Type 3. Figure 1 illustrates the amount of aid traversing each arc. Note that, due to the floods, the river course heavily influences the solution. The sizes of convoys traversing the arcs can be seen in Table 7.

Used arcs	Convoy size	Used arcs	Convoy size	Used arcs	Convoy size
<i>n1 – n12</i>	8	<i>n1 – n31</i>	3	<i>n2 – n13</i>	1
<i>n2 – n14</i>	7	<i>n2 – n33</i>	6	<i>n2 – n34</i>	2
<i>n2 – n36</i>	6	<i>n3 – n39</i>	10	<i>n3 – n41</i>	20
<i>n30 – n4</i>	2	<i>n30 – n5</i>	1	<i>n34 – n7</i>	1
<i>n33 – n8</i>	1	<i>n10 – n9</i>	3	<i>n10 – n13</i>	1
<i>n33 – n10</i>	5	<i>n35 – n11</i>	1	<i>n12 – n16</i>	3
<i>n36 – n15</i>	2	<i>n16 – n21</i>	1	<i>n36 – n17</i>	1
<i>n38 – n18</i>	2	<i>n37 – n19</i>	1	<i>n36 – n20</i>	3
<i>n40 – n22</i>	6	<i>n40 – n24</i>	1	<i>n41 – n25</i>	1
<i>n29 – n26</i>	4	<i>n41 – n27</i>	2	<i>n41 – n29</i>	17
<i>n31 – n30</i>	3	<i>n34 – n35</i>	1	<i>n38 – n37</i>	1
<i>n39 – n38</i>	3	<i>n39 – n40</i>	7		

Table 7: Compromise solution: arcs used and convoy sizes

Finally, we develop a sensitivity analysis by performing several additional experiments in which we modify the parameter values that are obtained through subjective elicitation (reliability and security). Table 8 shows the ideal and estimated nadir points. It also shows the compromise solutions obtained with the original data with neither reliability nor security nor both criteria. In these cases we omit the values of the ideal and

Figure 1: Compromise solution of the Pakistan test case

estimated nadir points for simplicity.

Comparing the compromise solutions, Table 8 shows how the attribute values of security and reliability worsen when they are not considered in the objective function. This supports the idea that taking security and reliability into account when solving the problem is important, but the particular parameter values used to characterize the arcs of the network in relation to these attributes are not as important. For instance, looking at a risk map, if there is a very secure area, another one with a very high security risk and a third one in between, the important issue is to represent the different risk perceptions through different parameter values. In the solution, this difference indicates which roads should be preferred or avoided.

6. Test cases

The previous section introduced the case of Pakistan floods in 2010. This case focuses on an extensive area (floods along the river) with a large but well-structured network and arcs that are restricted to some types of

	T	C	E	P	S	R
Original solution						
<i>Ideal point</i>	1.95	731.24	0.19	0.00	3.62	238.25
<i>Estimated nadir point</i>	7.24	1436.2	0.48	1.00	537.27	915.75
Compromise solution	4.04	1031.85	0.33	0.00	232.26	481.25
Without Reliability						
Compromise solution	4.04	1046.83	0.29	0.00	192.06	(516.25)
Without Security						
Compromise solution	4.04	926.97	0.29	0.12	(238.49)	477.25
Without Reliability and Security						
Compromise solution	4.04	1004.31	0.26	0.33	(262.37)	(526.50)
Changing Reliability (level 0.25→0.15, level 0.75→0.85)						
<i>Ideal point</i>	1.95	731.24	0.19	0.00	3.62	156.30
<i>Estimated nadir point</i>	7.24	1436.20	0.45	1.00	537.27	840.25
Compromise solution	4.04	981.40	0.29	0.00	301.50	410.35
Changing Security (level 0.92→0.9, level 0.90→0.5)						
<i>Ideal point</i>	1.95	731.24	0.19	0.00	3.12	238.25
<i>Estimated nadir point</i>	7.24	1436.20	0.48	1.00	320.92	915.75
Compromise solution	4.04	1025.08	0.33	0.15	162.86	486.25

Table 8: Pakistan test case: sensitivity analysis

vehicles. Besides the Pakistan case, we have built two more test cases using a similar format: Niger famine 2005
 340 and Haiti earthquake 2010. Each of the cases we prepared captures different aspects of post-disaster operations.
 The case of Niger is a small network covering an extensive area. It is a slow onset disaster (famine) that does
 not destroy infrastructure. The Haiti case is a very large sudden disaster. The earthquake partially destroys
 a complex urban network. There are security issues and there is still a high uncertainty about demand and
 reliability even after some weeks of disaster response. The mission assumes that a given number of camps is
 345 open and a fixed amount of aid can be distributed. Table 9 summarizes the key characteristics of the cases.
 While the Pakistan case has not been tested in published papers, the cases of Niger and Haiti have been used
 in articles already published, but neither the detailed case descriptions nor the (original and updated) data
 were publicly available until now.

Most of the data were retrieved from secondary sources on the Internet. One of the main online sources
 350 for logistics capacities is the LCA (Logistics Capacity Assessment) of the Logistics Cluster⁹. We use multiple
 websites to calculate the distance between villages or cities, such as Open Street Maps or Google Maps.
 However, it must be noted that many of these data sources either did not exist or did not have their current

⁹dlca.logcluster.org, [Last access: June 14th 2017]

Cases			
Place	Niger (Africa)	Haiti (America)	Pakistan (Asia)
Type of disaster	Famine	Earthquake	Floods
Year	2005	2010	2010
Geographic extension	Large	Small	Large
Network size	Small	Large	Large
Infrastructure damage	No damage	Large	Large
Security issues	Light	Yes	Yes

Table 9: Test Cases Summary

format and accuracy when some of the test cases were built. For example, the Humanitarian Reform created the cluster approach in 2005. The Logistic Cluster tools, as they work after 2005, were, therefore, not available for the Niger case. Reports from entities in the field and public websites such as *reliefweb* provided other data at the moment of the disaster. Based on the information provided in reports and media, subjective elicitation can estimate parameters such as the probability of assault or the reliability of arcs.

6.1. Niger famine (2005)

During 2005, Niger suffered a food crisis that affected 2.5 million people, including 800,000 children, who were already suffering malnutrition. The 2004 severe drought and locus plague that destroyed nearly all crops in some regions of the country exacerbated the endemic food insecurity and high prevalence of infectious diseases. These issues resulted in food scarcity that motivated the United Nations to warn the international community about the high risk that 3 million people would be suffering from famine by October 2005.

Based on the United Nations warnings, an organization plans a two-phase response to mitigate the effects of the food crisis (Farmamundi, 2005). Phase 1 focuses on food support for the affected population. The support consists of sugar, instant milk and peanut oil that serve as ingredients to prepare enriched porridge for malnourished children. Phase 2 concentrates on sanitary support. The organization supplies medicines for malaria, pneumonia and diarrhea to fulfill the demand at local health centers. Table 10 includes a brief description of the mission and other key information.

6.2. Haiti earthquake (2010)

On January 12th, 2010, Haiti suffered a catastrophic earthquake of magnitude 7.0 using the Richter scale. The epicenter was located 25 kilometers west of the capital, Port-au-Prince. The earthquake affected more than three million people, including 300,000 deaths, 350,000 injured and many more left homeless.

Niger	
Place	Niger (Africa)
Year	2005
Type of disaster	Famine
Organizations involved	Farmamundi, CADEV
N. affected people	2.5 million
Brief description: Niger suffers a food crisis aggravated by a locust plague in 2004 and drought in 2005. A relief organization led a two-phase response plan based on food and medical support.	
Mission: To distribute 500 tons of aid with a maximum budget of \$80,000 (EUR).	
Availability: 800 tons in Niamey, 500 tons in Gaya.	
Demand: 750 tons in Agadez, 300 tons in Zinder.	
Network and data: The transportation network includes the seven most important cities in the disaster area. Niamey (the capital) and Gaya are supply nodes. Dosso, Tahoua and Maradi are transshipment nodes. Agadez and Zinder are demand nodes. Eleven roads (each one associated with two directed arcs on opposite directions) connect the different nodes in the network. Distances between nodes, ransack probabilities and reliabilities of the arcs are available.	
Distances, Ransack probabilities, Reliability matrices and Available fleet (per city): available on the website www.mat.ucm.es/humlog .	
Data sources: Farmamundi (2005) and public websites such as Google Maps provide the data for this test case.	
Tested in: This test case was built as part of the final degree project of [37]. The case was tested in a peer reviewed paper by [31]. This article introduces a model based on two static network flows, using lexicographical goal programming to deal with different performance criteria.	
Further information: www.mat.ucm.es/humlog	

Table 10: Niger Test Case Description

Figure 2: Map of Haiti Test Case

Because of the level of devastation, many organizations collaborated in the humanitarian action to distribute large quantities of humanitarian aid. Aid was delivered over time by repeating the transport and distribution operations. The mission for this test case is defined considering one organization that distributes 150 tons of aid with a maximum budget of \$80,000 (USD). This is not aimed at satisfying the needs of all the affected population. Rather, it focuses on a small proportion of the total demand during a particular period of time. The mission can be repeated over time to satisfy, for instance, daily needs or even more than once per day. Table 11 includes a brief case summary.

We highlight that building a battery of test cases is a need in the field of humanitarian operations for both research and practice. New research findings in the area should be replicable and comparable to extant published work. Comparability requires running new models on public cases tested previously. Unfortunately, the area of humanitarian OR lacks public test cases, and the gap must be filled. With respect to practice, the credibility of academic results depends on practitioners' confidence in model assumptions, which are clearly stated in Section 4 and results obtained on test cases as the ones we present in Section 5.

7. Conclusions

Given the complexity of decision making during disaster relief operations, research in this area is increasingly important. Humanitarian organizations operate under adverse conditions, which requires the consideration of multiple performance criteria such as time, cost, equity and security, even though security remains under-examined in the literature. However, the lack of standardized test cases hinders the advance of research on

Haiti	
Place	Haiti (America)
Year	2010
Type of disaster	Earthquake
N. affected people	2 million
Brief description: A devastating 7.0 magnitude earthquake affected Haiti's most densely populated urban areas.	
Mission: To distribute 150 tons of aid with a maximum budget of \$80,000 (USD).	
Availability and demand: Available on the website www.mat.ucm.es/humlog .	
Network and data: The transportation network is composed of three nodes with available humanitarian aid (port, airport and Jimani city at the border with Dominican Republic), twelve transshipment nodes and nine demand nodes, which total 24 nodes and 42 arcs. In Figure 2, the supply nodes are in green and the demand nodes in red. Different colors and thicknesses are assigned to the arcs, depending on their reliability and road quality, respectively. Distances, Ransack probabilities, Reliabilities matrices and Available fleet (per city): See www.mat.ucm.es/humlog .	
Data sources: The network data come from a logistics map provided by the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) (as of January 31, 2010). The map includes the location of the supply nodes, the distribution sites or demand nodes (both secured by the US Joint Task Force and the United Nations Stabilization Mission in Haiti - MINUSTAH) and most of the transshipment nodes. The demand at each distribution site is estimated from a map showing the density of displaced people and field medical locations as of January 26, 2010. Figure 2 depicts the transportation network over a map provided by the Homeland Security Integrated Response Team (DHIRT) - UN MENUSTAH GIS - UN OSOCC/MAPACTION - U.S. HHS/USAID. Data regarding the characteristics and conditions of the road infrastructure are from two maps: (i) map reporting the "satellite-identified IDP concentrations, road and bridge obstacles in central Port-au-Prince, Haiti" as of January 12, 2010, created by the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR), and (ii) map focused only on the Port-au-Prince road conditions as of January 28, 2010, created by the World Food Programme (WFP) Emergency Preparedness Branch (ODEP).	
Tested in: The case is tested in [43], [40], [25] and [14]. The first article introduces an improved version of the model presented in [31], which is based on static network flow. The second article introduces a double dynamic network flow. Both articles propose goal programming models. The third article presents a hierarchical compromise model for the joint optimization of recovery operations and distribution of emergency goods, and the fourth article develops a GRASP method to solve the routing problem.	
Further information: www.mat.ucm.es/humlog	

Table 11: Haiti Test Case Description

disaster-response operations because it complicates replication, validation and comparison of results.

This paper makes two contributions to humanitarian OR. First, we develop a multi-criteria transportation model for last mile distribution of humanitarian aid that incorporates security as performance criteria. Regarding security, the routing model forces vehicles to travel together through the arcs forming convoys, which facilitates their protection and escort. The model assumptions entail limitations, although some can easily be mitigated. The constraint that all vehicles must traverse an arc at the same time may induce long waiting times but it is necessary to model convoys, which is the core of the model. However, as discussed above, this constraint can be relaxed via arc duplication. This would allow a larger number of convoys to traverse arcs at different times. Furthermore, the model optimizes transportation for a “general mission” to distribute the target load in one period. An implicit assumption is that vehicles make only one trip during the general mission. This could become a limitation if the mission included long trips and very short trips. To avoid mixing trips, the mission’s geographic region could be clustered in areas according to trip durations. In addition, to be useful in practice the model requires the implementation of a friendly interface linked to information systems as well as user training. Finally, data reliability, culture and other unforeseen circumstances could be an obstacle to implement the resulting distribution plan, which could still be used as a decision support tool. Even though it has limitations, this is the first multi-criteria model to produce a detailed vehicle schedule for convoys in humanitarian OR.

Our second contribution relates to data sharing. We prepare, standardize and share the raw data of three test cases for last mile distribution in the humanitarian context. Building test cases consumes resources and time. Over the years, we systematically collected realistic data on disasters. We share three test cases based on real disasters: Niger famine 2005, Haiti earthquake 2010 and Pakistan floods 2010. These realistic cases exhibit different characteristics of the humanitarian context. The three cases have supported research on humanitarian last mile distribution and two of them have provided input for papers that have been published in peer-reviewed journals. However, the detailed case descriptions, data granularity and updated data have been prepared for this article and were not made public until now. The three test cases are available on our website www.mat.ucm.es/humlog. We hope to maintain the website and increase the public data contained there such that the test cases become a reference for scholars of humanitarian OR and support their research. This initiative will also reduce requests for data and extra work for already busy humanitarian practitioners. We encourage other researchers to share their raw data through our website. This paper takes a first step towards building a battery of test cases for humanitarian OR. By sharing test cases, we encourage replicability and model comparison within the humanitarian OR community.

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Appendix A. Mathematical programming model

$$\min(TIME, COST, EQUI, PRIO, RELI, SECU) \quad (A.1)$$

Constraints (A.2) are those defining the criteria expressions:

$$TIME \geq T_{i, \text{deg}_i} \quad \forall i \quad (\text{A.2a})$$

$$COST = \sum_{k,j} \text{dist}_k (cv_{k,j} L_{k,j} + cf_{k,j} \sum_s X_{k,j,s}) + cu \sum_{j,s} (Q1_{j,s} + Q2_{j,s}) + \sum_{i,j} \text{cback}_{j,i} \left(\sum_{s,k|\text{end}_k=i} X_{k,j,s} - \sum_{s,k|\text{beg}_k=i} X_{k,j,s} \right) \quad (\text{A.2b})$$

$$COST \leq b \quad (\text{A.2c})$$

$$EQUI = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|i|\text{dem}_i > 0} \sum_{i|\text{dem}_i > 0} \left(\frac{S_{i, \text{deg}(i)}}{\text{dem}_i} - \text{idp} \right)^2} \quad (\text{A.2d})$$

$$PRIO = \sum_{i|\text{pri}_i > 0} \text{pri}_i \left(1 - \frac{S_{i, \text{deg}(i)}}{\text{dem}_i} \right) \quad (\text{A.2e})$$

$$AL_k = \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \left(\sum_{s'|\text{s} \leq s' < |A|} \max \left\{ 0, \sum_{k'} X_{k',j,s'} L_{k',j} - \sum_{k''} X_{k'',j,s'+1} L_{k'',j} \right\} + \sum_{k'} X_{k',j,|A|} L_{k',j} \right) \quad (\text{A.2f})$$

$$RELI = \sum_k (1 - r_k) AL_k \quad (\text{A.2g})$$

$$PR_k = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} = 0 \\ p_k + \frac{p_k - q_k}{(c_k - 1)^2} \left(\left(\sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \right)^2 - 2c_k \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} + 2c_k - 1 \right) & \text{if } 1 \leq \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \leq c_k \\ q_k & \text{if } \sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} > c_k \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.2h})$$

$$SECU = \sum_k PR_k \sum_j L_{k,j} \quad (\text{A.2i})$$

Note that reliability (A.2f) is a nonlinear measure since load values multiply the binary variables identifying that delivery is done after traversing the arc considered. This expression can be linearized, as it appears in the main text, replacing (A.2f) and (A.2g) by the following constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{k,j} &= \sum_s LS_{k,j,s} \\ LS_{k,j,s} &\leq cap_j X_{k,j,s} \\ Q1_{j,s} - Q2_{j,s} &= \sum_k LS_{k,j,s} - \sum_k LS_{k,j,s+1} \\ AL_{k,j,s} &\geq \sum_{s'|\text{s}' > \text{s}} Q1_{j,s'} - q_{global}(1 - X_{k,j,s}) \\ RELI &= \sum_k (1 - r_k) \sum_{j,s} AL_{k,j,s}. \end{aligned}$$

Constraints (A.3) are devoted to vehicle-arc relations. (A.3a)-(A.3b) force each vehicle to use at most one arc at each stage leaving the node reached at the previous stage. In (A.3c), if a vehicle does not move at a

particular stage, it cannot move at the next stage either.

$$\sum_k X_{k,j,s} \leq 1 \quad \forall j, \forall s \quad (\text{A.3a})$$

$$X_{k',j,s+1} \leq 1 - X_{k,j,s} \quad \forall j, \forall s < |A|, \forall k, k' \mid \text{beg}_{k'} \neq \text{end}_k \quad (\text{A.3b})$$

$$\sum_k X_{k,j,s+1} \leq \sum_k X_{k,j,s} \quad \forall j, \forall s < |A| \quad (\text{A.3c})$$

535 Constraints (A.4) are devoted to node events. (A.4a)-(A.4d) define the events in each node and arc. If there are no vehicles in an arc, no event is activated. Otherwise, the arrival and departure events are activated, as stated in (A.4e)-(A.4f).

$$\sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)} \leq 1 \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) > 0 \quad (\text{A.4a})$$

$$\sum_{e(i) > 0} Z_{i,k,e(i)} \leq 1 \quad \forall i, \forall k \quad (\text{A.4b})$$

$$\sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)+1} \leq \sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) \mid 0 < e(i) < \text{deg}_i \quad (\text{A.4c})$$

$$Z_{i,k,e(i)} = 0 \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) > 0, \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k \neq i, \text{end}_k \neq i \quad (\text{A.4d})$$

$$\sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \geq Z_{i,k,e(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) > 0, \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k = i \text{ or } \text{end}_k = i \quad (\text{A.4e})$$

$$\sum_{j,s} X_{k,j,s} \leq |V| \sum_{e(i) > 0} Z_{i,k,e(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k = i \text{ or } \text{end}_k = i \quad (\text{A.4f})$$

Constraints (A.5) are devoted to amounts of load vehicles carry. (A.5a) relates load and vehicle capacity. (A.5b)-(A.5c) assure that the vehicle carries some load at its last stage.

$$L_{k,j} \leq \text{cap}_j \sum_s X_{k,j,s} \quad \forall k, \forall j \quad (\text{A.5a})$$

$$L_{k,j} \geq X_{k,j,s} - \sum_{k'} X_{k',j,s+1} \quad \forall k, \forall j, \forall s < |A| \quad (\text{A.5b})$$

$$L_{k,j} \geq X_{k',j,|A|} \quad \forall k, \forall j \quad (\text{A.5c})$$

Constraints (A.6) are devoted to stocks. (A.6a)-(A.6b) (resp. (A.6c)-(A.6d)) assure that if an event corresponds to an outgoing (incoming) arc, the stock decreases (increases) in the amount of load carried through the arc. In (A.6e)-(A.6f), if an event does not correspond to any arc, the stock does not change. Notice that coefficients of qglobal in (A.6a)-(A.6f) provide the tightest bounds for the variation of the stocks and relax the constraints when needed. (A.6g) assures that the total amount of aid is distributed, whereas in (A.6h), the final stock

cannot exceed the demand at each node (except for supply nodes).

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \leq S_{i,e(i)} - \sum_j L_{k,j} + 2q_{\text{global}}(1 - Z_{i,k,e(i)+1}) \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i, \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k = i \quad (\text{A.6a})$$

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \geq S_{i,e(i)} - \sum_j L_{k,j} - q_{\text{global}}(1 - Z_{i,k,e(i)+1}) \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i, \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k \neq i \quad (\text{A.6b})$$

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \leq S_{i,e(i)} + \sum_j L_{k,j} + q_{\text{global}}(1 - Z_{i,k,e(i)+1}) \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i, \forall k \mid \text{end}_k = i \quad (\text{A.6c})$$

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \geq S_{i,e(i)} + \sum_j L_{k,j} - 2q_{\text{global}}(1 - Z_{i,k,e(i)+1}) \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i, \forall k \mid \text{end}_k \neq i \quad (\text{A.6d})$$

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \leq S_{i,e(i)} + q_{\text{global}} \sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)+1} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i \quad (\text{A.6e})$$

$$S_{i,e(i)+1} \geq S_{i,e(i)} - q_{\text{global}} \sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)+1} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i \quad (\text{A.6f})$$

$$\sum_{i \mid \text{dem}_i > 0} S_{i,\text{deg}_i} = q_{\text{global}} \quad (\text{A.6g})$$

$$S_{i,\text{deg}_i} \leq \text{dem}_i \quad \forall i \mid \text{qav}_i = 0 \quad (\text{A.6h})$$

Constraint (A.7) computes travel times as the maximum between the time required traveling to the speed of the arc and that one required by the speed of the slowest vehicle of the convoy.

$$D_k \geq \frac{\text{dist}_k}{\min\{\text{velc}_k, \text{velv}_j\}} X_{k,j,s} \quad \forall k, \forall j, \forall s \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Constraints (A.8) are devoted to event times. (A.8a) guarantees that the sequence of event times at each node is non-decreasing. In (A.8b) if an node event corresponds to an outgoing arc, its time must be after handling the loading and unloading in the node of the vehicles included in the departing convoy (notice that M is an upper bound for the operation time). In (A.8c), if an event of a node does not correspond to any arc, the event time is the same as in the preceding event. In (A.8d)-(A.8e), the event time corresponding to an incoming arc is the sum of the departing convoy time and the traveling time through the arc.

$$T_{i,e(i)+1} \geq T_{i,e(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i \quad (\text{A.8a})$$

$$T_{i,e'(i)} \geq T_{i,e(i)} + \text{tu}(Q1_{j,s} + Q2_{j,s}) - M(4 - X_{j,k,s} - Z_{i,k,e(i)} - X_{j,k',s+1} - Z_{i,k',e'(i)}) \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < e'(i) < \text{deg}_i, \forall j, \forall s, \quad \forall k, k' \mid \text{end}_k = i, \text{beg}_{k'} = i \quad (\text{A.8b})$$

$$T_{i,e(i)+1} \leq T_{i,e(i)} + M \sum_k Z_{i,k,e(i)+1} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i) < \text{deg}_i \quad (\text{A.8c})$$

$$T_{i',e(i')} \leq T_{i,e(i)} + D_k + M(2 - Z_{i,k,e(i)} - Z_{i',k,e(i')}) \quad \forall i, i', \forall e(i) > 0, e(i') > 0, \quad \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k = i, \text{end}_k = i' \quad (\text{A.8d})$$

$$T_{i',e(i')} \geq T_{i,e(i)} + D_k - M(2 - Z_{i,k,e(i)} - Z_{i',k,e(i')}) \quad \forall i, i', \forall e(i) > 0, e(i') > 0, \quad \forall k \mid \text{beg}_k = i, \text{end}_k = i' \quad (\text{A.8e})$$

Constraints (A.9) are devoted to relations between arcs. (A.9a)-(A.9c) assure the precedence relationships. In (A.9d) each arc utilized precedes all the arcs that the vehicle traverses afterwards. In (A.9e) (resp. (A.9f)), each incoming arc precedes (cannot be preceded by) the outgoing (incoming) arcs that correspond to later

events of the node. In (A.9g), each outgoing arc cannot be preceded by the arcs that correspond to later events of the node. Finally, Constraints (A.10) define the variables' types and fix the value of some variables.

$$P_{k,k} = 0 \quad \forall k \quad (\text{A.9a})$$

$$P_{k,k'} + P_{k',k} \leq 1 \quad \forall k, k' \quad (\text{A.9b})$$

$$P_{k,k''} \geq P_{k,k'} + P_{k',k''} - 1 \quad \forall k, k', k'' \quad (\text{A.9c})$$

$$P_{k,k'} \geq X_{k,j,s} + X_{k',j,s'} - 1 \quad \forall k, k', \forall j, \forall s, s' \mid s < s' \quad (\text{A.9d})$$

$$P_{k,k'} \geq Z_{i,k,e(i)} + Z_{i,k',e'(i)} - 1 \quad \forall i, \forall e(i), e'(i) \mid 0 < e(i) < e'(i), \quad \forall k, k' \mid \text{end}_k = i, \text{beg}_{k'} = i \quad (\text{A.9e})$$

$$P_{k',k} \leq 2 - Z_{i,k,e(i)} - Z_{i,k',e'(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i), e'(i) \mid 0 < e(i) < e'(i), \quad \forall k, k' \mid \text{end}_k = i, \text{end}_{k'} = i \quad (\text{A.9f})$$

$$P_{k',k} \leq 2 - Z_{i,k,e(i)} - Z_{i,k',e'(i)} \quad \forall i, \forall e(i), e'(i) \mid 0 < e(i) < e'(i), \quad \forall k, k' \mid \text{beg}_k = i, (\text{beg}_{k'} = i \text{ or } \text{end}_{k'} = i) \quad (\text{A.9g})$$

$$X_{k,j,s} = 0 \quad \forall k, \forall j, \forall s \mid \text{comp}_{k,j} = 0 \quad (\text{A.10a})$$

$$X_{k,j,1} = 0 \quad \forall k, \forall j \mid \text{beg}_k \neq \text{ori}_j \quad (\text{A.10b})$$

$$X_{k,j,s}, Z_{i,k,e(i)}, P_{k,k'} \in \{0, 1\}, Z_{i,k,0} = 0 \quad (\text{A.10c})$$

$$L_{k,j}, S_{i,e(i)}, T_{i,e(i)}, D_k \geq 0, S_{i,0} = \text{qay}_i, T_{i,0} = 0 \quad (\text{A.10d})$$